

OntoFoCE and ObE Forensics. Email-traceability supporting tools for Digital Forensics

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Supplementary material: OntoFoCE SPARQL QUERIES

Below are the SPARQL queries corresponding to the 21 questions of competence of OntoFoCE.

<p><i>CQ01: Given an email, what is the date and time when the email was sent and the sender's IP address?</i></p> <pre>PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#> SELECT DISTINCT ?dateSending ?ipAddress WHERE { ?email oc:emailHasSequence ?s. ?s oc:sequenceHasThread ?h. ?h oc:threadHasOccurrence ?o. ?o rdf:type oc:SendingOccurrence. ?o oc:dateTimeOccurrence ?dateSending. ?o oc:occurrenceTakesPlaceInDevice?q. ?q oc:deviceHasId?ip. ?ip oc:idDevice?ipAddress. FILTER (?email =oc:EMAIL_C1).}</pre>
<p><i>CQ02: Given an email, is the date and time when the email was sent and the recipient's IP address?</i></p> <pre>PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#> SELECT DISTINCT ?dateReceiving ?ipAddress WHERE { ?email oc:emailHasSequence ?s. ?s oc:sequenceHasThread ?h. ?h oc:threadHasOccurrence ?o. ?o rdf:type oc:ReceivingOccurrence. ?o oc:dateTimeOccurrence?dateReceiving. ?o oc:occurrenceTakesPlaceInDevice?q. ?q oc: deviceHasId ?ip. ? ip oc:idDevice?ipAddress. FILTER (?email=oc:EMAIL_C1).}</pre>
<p><i>CQ03: Given an email, what accounts was the email sent to?</i></p> <pre>PREFIX owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#> PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#> SELECT ?alias ?Account WHERE { ?account oc:recipientAccountReceivedEmail ?email. ?account rdf:type oc:RecipientAccount. OPTIONAL {?account oc:aliasUser ?alias}. ?account oc:emailAccount ?Account. FILTER (?email=oc:EMAIL_C1).}</pre>
<p><i>CQ04: Given an email, what is the user alias and email address of the Sender?</i></p> <pre>PREFIX owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#> PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#> SELECT ?alias ?account WHERE { ?accountSending oc:senderAccountSendsEmail ?email. ?accountSending rdf:type oc:SenderAccount. OPTIONAL {?accountSending oc:aliasUser ?alias}. ?accountSending oc:emailAccount ?account. FILTER (?email=oc:EMAIL_C1).}</pre>
<p><i>CQ05: Given an email, what is the user alias and email address of the Recipient?</i></p> <pre>PREFIX owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#> PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#> SELECT ?alias ?account WHERE { ?accountReceiving oc:recipientAccountReceivedEmail ?email. ?accountReceiving rdf:type oc:RecipientAccount. OPTIONAL {?accountReceiving oc:aliasUser ?alias}. ?accountReceiving oc:emailAccount ?account. FILTER (?email=oc:EMAIL_C1).}</pre>
<p><i>CQ06: Given an email, what was the email client used by each user?</i></p> <pre>PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#> SELECT DISTINCT ?account ?alias ?client WHERE {{ ?accountReceiver oc:recipientAccountReceivedEmail ?email.</pre>

```

?accountReceiver oc:emailAccount ?account.
?accountReceiver oc:receivesIn ?cli.
?cli oc:emailClientName ?client.
?accountReceiver rdf:type oc:RecipientAccount.
OPTIONAL {?accountReceiver oc:aliasUser ?alias .}
UNION
{ ?accountSending oc:senderAccountSendsEmail ?email.
?accountSending oc:emailAccount ?account.
?accountSending oc:sendsFrom ?cli.
?cli oc:emailClientName ?client.
?accountSending rdf:type oc:SenderAccount.
OPTIONAL {?accountSending oc:aliasUser ?alias .}
FILTER (?email=oc:EMAIL_C1).}

```

CQ07: Given an email, what device was the email sent from?

```

PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?Device ?macAddressDevice ?ipAddress
WHERE { ?email oc:emailHasSequence ?s.
?s oc:sequenceHasThread ?h.
?h oc:threadHasOccurrence ?o.
?o rdf:type oc:SendingOccurrence.
?o oc:occurrenceTakesPlaceInDevice ?equip.
?equip oc:deviceHasId ?IP.
?IP oc:idDevice ?ipAddress.
OPTIONAL {?equip oc:macAddressDevice ?macAddressDevice .}
?equip oc:descriptionDevice ?Device.
FILTER (?email=oc:EMAIL_C1).}

```

CQ08: Given an email, what device was the email received on?

```

PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?Device ?macAddressDevice ?ipAddress
WHERE { ?email oc:emailHasSequence ?s.
?s oc:sequenceHasThread ?h.
?h oc:threadHasOccurrence ?o.
?o rdf:type oc:ReceivingOccurrence.
?o oc:occurrenceTakesPlaceInDevice ?equip.
?equip oc:macAddressDevice ?macAddressDevice.
?equip oc:deviceHasId ?IP.
?IP oc:idDevice ?ipAddress.
?equip oc:descriptionDevice ?Device.
FILTER (?email=oc:EMAIL_C1).}

```

CQ09: Given an email, a sender S and a recipient R, what is the sequence of devices through which this email traveled?

```

PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?occurrence ?date ?ipAddress ?Device
WHERE { ?sender oc:senderAccountSendsEmail ?email.
?sender oc:senderAccountUsesSenderDevice ?equipS.
?receiver oc:recipientAccountReceivedEmail ?email.
?receiver oc:recipientAccountUsesRecipientDevice ?equipR.
?o oc:occurrenceTakesPlaceInDevice ?equip.
?email oc:emailHasSequence ?s1.
?s1 oc:sequenceHasThread ?t1.
?t1 oc:threadHasOccurrence ?occurrence.
?occurrence oc:occurrenceTakesPlaceInDevice ?equipo2.
?equipo2 oc:deviceHasId ?IP.
?equipo2 oc:descriptionDevice ?Device.
?IP oc:idDevice ?ipAddress.
?occurrence oc:dateTimeOccurrence ?date.
FILTER (?receiver=oc:ACCOUNT_R1 && ?sender=oc:ACCOUNT_S1 && ?email =oc:EMAIL_C1).
} order by ?date

```

CQ10: Given an account A, what emails did it send?

```

PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?emails ?subject ?sendingDate ?accountRecipient
WHERE { ?account oc:senderAccountSendsEmail ?emails.
?accountR oc:recipientAccountReceivedEmail ?emails.
?accountR oc:emailAccount ?accountRecipient.
?emails oc:emailHasSequence ?s.
?s oc:sequenceHasThread ?h.
?h oc:threadHasOccurrence ?o.

```

```
?o oc:occurrenceHasEmailSubject ?a.  
?a oc:contentsEmailSubject ?subject.  
?o rdf:type oc:SendingOccurrence.  
?o oc:dateTimeOccurrence ?sendingDate.  
FILTER (?account=oc:ACCOUNT_S1)}
```

CQ11: Given an account A, what emails did it receive?

```
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>  
PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#>  
SELECT DISTINCT ?email ?subject ?sendingDate ?sender  
WHERE { ?account oc:recipientAccountReceivedEmail ?email.  
?email oc:emailHasSequence ?s.  
?email oc:emailSentBySenderAccount ?accountS.  
?accountS oc:emailAccount ?sender.  
?s oc:sequenceHasThread ?h.  
?h oc:threadHasOccurrence ?o.  
?o oc:occurrenceHasEmailSubject ?a.  
?a oc:contentsEmailSubject ?subject.  
?o rdf:type oc:ReceivingOccurrence.  
?o oc:dateTimeOccurrence ?sendingDate.  
FILTER (?account=oc:ACCOUNT_R1).}
```

CQ12: Given an account A1, has an email been sent to account A2?

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>  
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>  
PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#>  
SELECT DISTINCT ?email ?subject ?sendingDate  
WHERE { ?accountC1 oc:senderAccountSendsEmail ?email.  
?accountC2 oc:recipientAccountReceivedEmail ?email.  
?accountC1 oc:emailAccount ?accountS.  
?accountC2 oc:emailAccount ?accountR.  
?email oc:emailHasSequence ?s.  
?s oc:sequenceHasThread ?h.  
?h oc:threadHasOccurrence ?o.  
?o rdf:type oc:SendingOccurrence.  
?o oc:occurrenceHasEmailSubject ?a.  
?o oc:dateTimeOccurrence ?sendingDate.  
?a oc:contentsEmailSubject ?subject.  
FILTER (?accountC1=oc:ACCOUNT_S1 && ?accountC2=oc:ACCOUNT_R2).}
```

CQ13: Given an account A1, has an email been received from account A2?

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>  
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>  
PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#>  
SELECT DISTINCT ?email ?subject ?receivingDate  
WHERE { ?accountC1 oc:recipientAccountReceivedEmail ?email.  
?accountC2 oc:senderAccountSendsEmail ?email.  
?email oc:emailHasSequence ?s.  
?s oc:sequenceHasThread ?h.  
?h oc:threadHasOccurrence ?o.  
?o rdf:type oc:ReceivingOccurrence.  
?o oc:dateTimeOccurrence ?receivingDate.  
?o oc:occurrenceHasEmailSubject ?a.  
?a oc:contentsEmailSubject ?subject.  
FILTER (?accountC1=oc:ACCOUNT_R2 && ?accountC2=oc:ACCOUNT_S1).}
```

CQ14: Given an IP address, what is its geographic location?

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>  
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>  
PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#>  
SELECT ?ipAddress ?localization WHERE { ?IP oc:geolocationIP ?localization.  
?IP oc:idDevice ?ipAddress.  
FILTER (?IP=oc:ID_SERVER_1).}
```

CQ15: What emails traveled through the device that has a given IP?

```
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>  
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>  
PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#>  
SELECT DISTINCT ?Device ?emailHeader WHERE { ?Device oc:deviceHasId ?IP.  
?occurrence oc:occurrenceTakesPlaceInDevice ?Device.  
?h oc:threadHasOccurrence ?occurrence.  
?s oc:sequenceHasThread ?h.  
?email oc:emailHasSequence ?s.  
?e oc:senderAccountSendsEmail ?email.  
?IP oc:idDevice ?address.}
```

?occurrence oc:occurrenceHasEmailHeader ?emailHeader.
FILTER regex(?address,"209.85.208.170").}

CQ16: What emails were sent from a certain account on a given date?

PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?email ?accountReceiver ?subject ?date
WHERE { ?account rdf:type oc:SenderAccount.
?account oc:senderAccountSendsEmail ?email.
?email oc:emailHasSequence ?s.
?s oc:sequenceHasThread ?h.
?occurrence oc:occurrenceBelongsToThread ?h.
?occurrence oc:occurrenceHasEmailSubject ?a.
?a oc:contentsEmailSubject ?subject.
?occurrence rdf:type oc:SendingOccurrence.
?occurrence oc:dateTimeOcurrence ?date.
?accountR oc:recipientAccountReceivedEmail ?email.
?accountR oc:emailAccount ?accountReceiver.
FILTER(("2018-07-08T15:41:46"^^xsd:date=?date) &&
(?account=oc:ACCOUNT_S1)).}

CQ17: What emails were received by a certain account on a given date?

PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?email ?accountSending ?accountReceiver ?subject ?date
WHERE { ?account rdf:type oc:SenderAccount.
?account oc:emailAccount ?accountSending.
?account oc:senderAccountSendsEmail ?email.
?email oc:emailHasSequence ?s.
?s oc:sequenceHasThread ?h.
?occurrence oc:occurrenceBelongsToThread ?h.
?occurrence oc:occurrenceHasEmailSubject ?a.
?a oc:contentsEmailSubject ?subject.
?occurrence rdf:type oc:SendingOccurrence.
?occurrence oc:dateTimeOcurrence ?date.
?accountR oc:recipientAccountReceivedEmail ?email.
?accountR oc:emailAccount ?accountReceiver.
FILTER(("2018-07-08T15:41:46"^^xsd:date=?date) && (?accountR=oc:ACCOUNT_R1)).}

CQ18: Given a keyword, does it appear in the subject of an email?

PREFIX owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?email ?subject ?date WHERE { ?email oc:emailHasSequence ?s.
?s oc:sequenceHasThread ?h.
?h oc:threadHasOccurrence ?occurrence.
?occurrence rdf:type oc:ReceivingOccurrence.
?occurrence oc:occurrenceHasEmailSubject ?a.
?occurrence oc:dateTimeOcurrence ?date.
?a oc:contentsEmailSubject ?subject.
?a oc:emailSubjectContainsKeyword ?keyWord.
?keyWord oc:contentsKeyword ?kw.
FILTER regex(?kw,"Colaboración").}

CQ19: Given a keyword, does it appear in the body of an email?

PREFIX owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?email ?body ?date WHERE { ?email oc:emailHasSequence ?s.
?s oc:sequenceHasThread ?h.
?h oc:threadHasOccurrence ?occurrence.
?occurrence rdf:type oc:ReceivingOccurrence.
?occurrence oc:occurrenceHasEmailBody ?a.
?occurrence oc:dateTimeOcurrence ?date.
?a oc:contentsEmailBody ?body.
?a oc:emailBodyContainsKeyword ?keyWord.
?keyWord oc:contentsKeyword ?kw.
FILTER regex(?kw,"Colaboración").}

CQ20: Given a keyword, does it appear in an email attachment?

PREFIX owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#>

```

PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?email ?attachment ?date WHERE { ?email oc:emailHasSequence ?s.
?s oc:sequenceHasThread ?h.
?h oc:threadHasOccurrence ?occurrence.
?occurrence rdf:type oc:ReceivingOccurrence.
?occurrence oc:occurrenceHasEmailAttachment ?a.
?occurrence oc:dateTimeOcurrence ?date.
?a oc:contentsEmailAttachment ?attachment.
?a oc:emailAttachmentContainsKeyword ?keyWord.
?keyWord oc:contentsKeyword ?kw.
FILTER regex(?kw,"Colaboración").}

```

CQ21: What emails were exchanged between accounts A1 and A2 in a given date range?

```

PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
PREFIX oc: <http://www.semanticweb.org/beatr/ontologies/2018/0/ontologia_correos#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?acSending1 ?acReceiver1 ?subject1 ?date1 ?acSender2
?acReceiver2 ?subject2 ?date2
WHERE {{ ?accountC1 oc:senderAccountSendsEmail ?email1.
?accountC1 oc:emailAccount ?acSending1.
?accountC2 oc:recipientAccountReceivedEmail ?email1.
?accountC2 oc:emailAccount ?acReceiver1.
?email1 oc:emailHasSequence ?s.
?s oc:sequenceHasThread ?h.
?h oc:threadHasOccurrence ?o.
?o oc:occurrenceHasEmailSubject ?a.
?a oc:contentsEmailSubject ?subject1.
?o rdf:type oc:SendingOccurrence.
?o oc:dateTimeOcurrence ?date1.
FILTER (?accountC1=oc:ACCOUNT_S1 && ?accountC2=oc:ACCOUNT_R1).
FILTER("2018-06-05"^^xsd:dateTime <= ?date1 && ?date1 <
"2019-02-24"^^xsd:dateTime) }
UNION {
?accountC3 oc:senderAccountSendsEmail ?email2.
?accountC3 oc:emailAccount ?acSender2.
?accountC4 oc:recipientAccountReceivedEmail ?email2.
?accountC4 oc:emailAccount ?acReceiver2.
?account2 oc:emailHasSequence ?s2.
?s2 oc:sequenceHasThread ?h2.
?h2 oc:threadHasOccurrence ?o2.
?o2 oc:occurrenceHasEmailSubject ?a2.
?a2 oc:contentsEmailSubject ?subject2.
?o2 rdf:type oc:SendingOccurrence.
?o2 oc:dateTimeOcurrence ?date2.
FILTER (?accountC3=oc:ACCOUNT_S1 && ?accountC4=oc:ACCOUNT_R1).
FILTER("2018-06-05"^^xsd:dateTime <= ?date2 && ?date2 <
"2019-02-24"^^xsd:dateTime) }}

```